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DIGITALIZATION AS THE BASIS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF ENTERPRISES IN THE HOSPITALITY INDUSTRY

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ABSTRACT

Digitization is becoming the main trend, which is clearly manifested in the distribution models of hotel services, and is also actively entering the field of automation of internal business processes. The number pool and public areas are also automated. Today, a modern hotel is a place where everything is created exclusively for the convenience and comfort of customers. Digital innovations are gradually becoming the new standard of hotel service. But in addition to two obvious trends - the development of mobile services for guests and the launch of services based on gadgets, the digitalization of hotels also includes the implementation of advanced solutions for analytics and security.

Keywords: digitization, automatic systems, hotel and restaurant business, tourism, hospitality industry.

Formulation of the problem.

Information technologies are of great importance for almost all spheres of the economy. In today's conditions, these technologies have found widespread use in the hospitality industry, and the artificial intelligence market is growing every year. In order to be commercially successful in today's economic conditions, various significant innovative computer technologies (clouds, mobile services, big data analytics, highly loaded systems) have been developed. In today's conditions, the hospitality industry is a branch of economic activity that provides a tenth of the global gross product and is developing at a rapid pace and in the coming years may become one of the most important sectors of

business activity. The hospitality industry is the field of meeting the needs of services related to recreation and organization of activities during travel.

POS systems, hotel digital security systems are responsible for collecting and analyzing different levels of visitor data. Using this information, hotels can encourage regular customers and draw conclusions about customer behavior and preferences, prepare advanced analytics. Digital security systems can not only monitor the smallest violations of public order, but also, for example, provide additional information.

Analysis of recent research and publications.

To date, the issues of the article have been sufficiently well researched and the research results have

been reflected in the works of such authors as M. Burgin, L. Vashchenko, G. Gerasimova, L. Danylenko, L. Podymova, O. Popova, A. Khutorskyi, A. Nikols and other. The study of the problems of the development of the tourism and hotel-restaurant industry has received great attention from domestic scientists and specialists, namely: O. Golovko, G. Krul, M. Malska, L. Nechayuk, O. Shapovalova.

The purpose of the work.

The problems and prospects of the development of the market of information and information technologies at enterprises of the hospitality industry are considered.

Results.

The hospitality industry is one of the main components of the economy of Ukraine. In today's conditions, the service sector, like any other, is constantly transformed under the influence of globalization and integration of processes. Thus, the effective functioning of the hospitality industry is an indicator of positive changes in the state's economy, an important prerequisite for the intensification of international relations and the country's integration into the world community [1].

The modern informational development of society is undergoing innovation-technological, oriented transformations, in particular, this applies to the service sector. The main goal of these transformations is primarily convenience, accessibility, mobility, awareness and good relations with its customers.

Monitoring and analysis of the global experience of hospitality industry enterprises demonstrates a constant increase in the popularity of this business sector and causes an increase in the harshness of survival conditions. This situation forces institutions to constantly turn to innovative technological developments in order to maintain competitiveness in the market, fight for the loyalty of the guest, improve the quality of service, and also expand the range of services provided.

Constantly growing competition in the service market requires special uniqueness and individuality from service companies. It is the innovative approach to the introduction of the latest information developments in the activities of hospitality industry enterprises that is a necessary condition for their effective functioning. The introduction of new information services and products will contribute to the effective use of all opportunities for quality service and maximizing the potential of the hospitality industry.

The introduction of the latest information technologies in the development of production or in the management of enterprises of the hospitality industry makes it possible to significantly increase the efficiency and effectiveness of work, through best practices, management methods or scientific knowledge. The advantage in terms of relevance is given to information technologies, since their use is a necessary condition for the functioning of any modern means of accommodation or catering enterprise, ensuring accuracy, efficiency, high speed of processing and transmission of information [3].

To ensure leadership and obtain competitive advantages in the market of hotel and restaurant services,

it is necessary to use computer networks, Internet technologies, end-to-end automation of all business processes [4].

Innovative activity is an important means of maintaining the level of competitiveness of any economic system [2, 4]. However, the implementation of information innovations in the practice of hospitality industry enterprises faces a number of factors, such as the risk of loss of capital investments, lack of experience with the introduction of innovations, lack of stimulation of innovations by the state, limited financial resources of entrepreneurs, high cost of innovative developments, etc. [5].

Online services are the main area where information technology advances are transforming the hospitality industry and bringing customer service to a qualitatively new level.

The use of information technologies for processing and transmitting information at enterprises in the service sector allows creating an innovative and adapted to modern conditions tourism product, which aims to increase competitiveness and, accordingly, increase the rate of expected profitability.

Specialists of the modern information sphere are sure that no company in the hospitality industry can do without the use of computer systems in today's conditions. Increasing the value of information as a product determines the progressive development of the information services industry in the hotel and restaurant industry. Ensuring a high level of guest service at enterprises of the hospitality industry in modern conditions cannot be achieved without the use of innovative technologies that involve the automation of many processes, electronic reservation, and the introduction of technologies that improve the quality of service while reducing staff [3].

The constantly progressive development of modern information technologies led to the emergence of completely new integrated computer management systems for enterprises in the hospitality industry. Today, systems based on the application of networks of personal computers and mini-computers with a developed interface are widely used [2]. This information flow makes it possible to exchange information.

One of the newest information technologies of today is SMM (Social Media Marketing) - the most popular type of promotion and trade of tourist products through social networks. It does not require large costs, is effective in use and easy to master for the personnel of service enterprises. Its main goal is to create individuality, recognition, branding of the enterprise; increasing interest in the services provided, facilitating communication with clients, expanding the client base and potential opportunities of the enterprise.

Promotion of hotel and restaurant services in social networks is necessary in order to find potential guests and increase the loyalty of regular customers. In other words, a good service social media profile should attract guests visually: good photos of food, videos of events, photos of staff and guests. Also, social networks are the latest platform for advertising mailings and integrations. Such advertising activity allows you to significantly save the budget and get a more effective result.

Businesses in the hospitality industry need SMM for the following purposes:

- to form a brand image;
- attract new customers;
- inform and maintain communication with guests;
- collect reviews.

Today, many enterprises of the hospitality industry have their profiles on such social networks as "Instagram" and "Facebook". This requires constant efforts to maintain a correct profile, update information and promote on online platforms. Also, these profiles provide an opportunity to quickly react to market changes:

- brand promotion;
- increasing the loyalty and popularity of the product/service;
- order service online;
- responding to feedback and suggestions;
- conducting raffles or quizzes with the aim of attracting new users of services (giveaway);
- increase in website traffic;
- providing services in compliance with quarantine requirements (ordering food online, food boxes, booking tickets, reserving tables in a restaurant, etc.).

The goods of service enterprises in SMM are the same services and goods that are presented in ordinary marketing. But it is Internet marketing that helps promote products, analyze the demand and supply of competitors, and in some cases test the product [3]. This type of marketing is a modern and extremely effective communication tool of a hotel or restaurant because the page/site has an optimal structure, all sections contain only relevant information that is constantly updated [6].

This type of information innovation had no effect on the price change. And the choice of products or services has become easier and more accessible for consumers.

Social Media Marketing makes it possible to choose the target audience in a more targeted manner, to choose relevant platforms where exactly this audience is represented to a greater extent. Due to high development rates, hospitality industry enterprises that have profiles in social networks are less sensitive to the crisis.

SMM first of all requires the latest knowledge and skills to work on online platforms. So, to promote a hotel or restaurant page in social networks, you need the following: determine the target audience, choose the appropriate social network, draw up a content plan, etc. To draw up a content plan, you must first determine what potential consumers of hotel and restaurant services need to know, and then divide the content into categories and formats. After the rubrics are formed, it is worth starting to develop the content plan of the enterprise. It can be laid out in calendar format or as a table.

A restaurant's content plan shouldn't be limited to just posts about food: posts can include information about different types of food, ingredients, veganism, favorite foods, even the features and history of the building in which the restaurant is located.

It is worth noting that the ever-increasing digitalization of all processes, especially in the enterprises of the hospitality industry, is increasingly embracing the digital environment, forming new boundaries of cus-

tom experience. At the same time, the customer experience is understood as the whole set of emotions, impressions and knowledge of the customer, which he receives at various points of contact (touchpoint) with the enterprise of the hotel and restaurant business (both real and virtual) [4].

SMM technologies at enterprises in the service sector contribute to strengthening the emotional connection with the client, increasing client orientation and helping to overcome all modern crisis situations with less losses.

Online booking is one of the latest information technologies that is being actively implemented in the activities of hospitality industry enterprises. Most service representatives now consider it necessary to have an online booking option for customers. This service requires qualitatively developed software: appropriate mobile applications and sites with a simple interface [6].

Modern enterprises of the hospitality industry are a complex complex of functional links. Taking into account the ever-growing competition and the latest directions in the field of service, the need to create conditions for prompt and efficient work of personnel increases. The solution to this problem is possible only through the implementation of hotel automation systems, that is, the introduction of Automated Management Systems (ACS) by the hotel (in the English version - Property Management System (PMS)) [3].

Automated management systems for hospitality industry enterprises are a complex of integrated subsystems that create an effective environment for the interaction of employees, clients and business partners - travel agencies, corporate clients and tour operators [2, 6].

Today, the most common automated hotel systems used in global practice are [1, 4]:

- Hotel management system (PMS - Property Management System);
- Restaurant management system (Point Of Sales);
- Event management system (Sales & Catering);
- Telephone service system (Telephone Management System);
- System of electronic keys (Key System);
- System of electronic minibars (Mini bar System);
- System of interactive television (Video Services System);
- Energy management system (Energy Management System);
- Credit Card Authorization System;
- Warehouse accounting and costing system (Food & Beverage);
- Financial accounting system (Accounting System);
- Central Reservation System (Central Reservation System);
- Internet reservation system (Web Reservation System);
- Personnel accounting system (Human Resource System);
- Security System (Security System).

Virtually all Western hotel software vendors have a version of their PMS specifically designed for remote use. These systems are developed using Internet tech-

nologies: ASP (Application Server Provider) and "client-server" based on SQL (Standard Query Language) [2].

One of the most common ACS today is the Amadeus system. It was created in 1987 by the largest European airlines Air France, Iberia, Lufthansa, SAS and is one of the largest and most widespread reservation systems. The network center is located in Germany (near Munich) and is connected to users all over the world thanks to its own reliable, high-speed communication network. It allows travel agencies to offer a full set of programs and the possibility of booking hotel seats, which ensures that enterprises are more flexible and productive in the modern service market [3].

Amadeus is now the leading computer reservation system in Europe. As a result of the acquisition of the System One reservation system in 1995, it is actively advancing to the American market.

Amadeus provides a variety of services, including cooperation with airlines, railway and ferry transportation, car rental, hotels, and also provides additional services, such as tourist insurance, etc. Amadeus is used by more than 30,000 travel agencies (more than 100,000 terminals), more than 400 airlines (more than 60,000 terminals).

More and more companies in the hospitality industry are turning to Amadeus services. This system provides open access to online booking 24/7, 365 days a year.

The basic advantages of the Amadeus system are:

- saving time due to the openness and availability of tourist, client and agency information;
- cost savings due to maximum efficiency as a result of stable operation and immediate confirmations;
- constant monitoring and control of the integrated flexible system meets all the needs of the agency in the work process;
- hourly updating of relevant information in real time;
- increase in income due to a wide range of opportunities that ensure the satisfaction of the entire range of customer orders [4].

Automated management systems of hospitality industry enterprises in today's conditions should not be products that are aimed exclusively at internal processes. It is important to ensure their relationship with external sources. Among the main ones [3]:

- payment systems - guests should be able to make payments using all available methods, for which it is necessary to install fiscal registers in the hotel;
- security and safety - we are talking about gaining access to certain premises, control of visits by outsiders;
- energy saving - hotel engineering systems and equipment are connected to the general automation program, this will save resources (for example, turning off power to unoccupied rooms, setting the desired temperature level depending on the presence or absence of a guest in the room);

- GDS systems - if the establishment is registered in them, then the internal automated hotel management systems must transfer the changed data about the room stock (occupied or free, price, etc.) to external global platforms, which will avoid overbooking (using the Channel Manager tool).

Modern service IT technologies are global reservation systems and CRM systems. They allow the client to choose the most convenient accommodation option for himself, taking into account all the advantages. The basis of CRM technology is the accumulation of information about the client and the management of this data. Customer databases make it possible to study the hotel's target audience in detail, forecast the demand for services, and conduct an effective marketing policy.

Conclusions. Therefore, the key basis for ensuring competitiveness, constant development and increasing the efficiency of the functioning of enterprises of the hospitality industry in Ukraine is the introduction of information technologies. This is cost-effective and efficient, as they contribute to improving the service process, reducing costs and generating additional income.

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